

BIOCOMPATIBILITY AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF HYDROXYAPATITE/TITANIA BIO-NANOCOMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

Significant progress in “nanochemistry” has given birth to a newly emerging area called “nanohybrid” or “nanocomposite” materials, which results from the modification of molecular level interactions of different inorganic components to form new, unique functional materials with better properties¹. In recent years, with the growing necessity for biomaterials, hydroxyapatite $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, abbreviated as HAp, has received extensive attention for its use as bone filler and implant material due to its excellent biocompatibility, close chemical and crystallographic structure with the mineral phase of natural bone². Hydroxyapatite is not only a main component of hard tissues, such as bones and teeth, but a material applied for bioceramics and adsorbents because it has an excellent affinity to biomaterials such as proteins³. Studies have shown that the properties of the ceramics could be improved remarkably by making one dimensional (1-D) nanoscale building blocks such as nanorods, nanofibers and nanotubes^{4,5}.

It has been reported that titania and HAp represent a good combination for functionally graded materials providing a gradient of bioactivity and good mechanical properties⁶. In addition to the bioactive properties, hydroxyapatite has great sorption properties, which are of great importance for both environmental processes and various industrial purposes including fertilizer production, water purification, degradation of pollutants and fabrication of biocompatible ceramics⁷. The phenomena of photo-induced electronic excitation in HAp is similar to the phenomena of photocatalysis in TiO_2 , which is a well established material used for the degradation of organic molecules⁸. TiO_2 have been investigated extensively for the killing or growth inhibition of bacteria^{9, 10}. Hence, a combination of HAp and TiO_2 to form a composite has the ability to absorb and decompose bacteria and organic

materials and is considered to be good in antibacterial applications and environmental purifications and also for photocatalytic decomposition of biomaterials, such as proteins and lipids¹¹⁻¹³.

In the field of biomedical, many failures in the implantation are may be due to the formation of microbes in the implanted site. If the implant material has the capability of antimicrobial activity within them, then the problem of failure will be reduced. Moreover, microbes which cause a wide variety of infections in humans and other animals can spread through common places like bathroom tiles, doorknobs, packing materials etc., can be controlled by the antimicrobial materials and coatings.

The present work is mainly focused on the biocompatibility and antimicrobial activity of the hydroxyapatite/ TiO_2 nanocomposites which was synthesized by combined high gravity and hydrothermal treatment of colloidal HAp and TiO_2 solutions. Different concentrations of HAp and TiO_2 were employed to prepare the composites. A model animal cell was used to study the cell compatibility of various HAp/ TiO_2 nanocomposite powders. The antimicrobial activity was tested by well-diffusion method against pathogenic organisms such as *Escherichia coli* (*E-coli*) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S-aureus*). The structural and morphological analysis was carried out in order to confirm the composite and nanostructure formation.

2 Materials and Method

2.1. Synthesis of HAp/ TiO_2 bio-nano-composites

The detailed preparation method and the principle of high gravity method were given in our previous report¹⁴. In brief, calcium nitrate ($\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and diammonium hydrogen phosphate ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$) were used as calcium and phosphate sources, respectively. Calcium and phosphate

solutions were prepared separately and mixed through the high gravity method to form hydroxyapatite. The pH of the phosphate solution was increased to 9 by adding ammonium hydroxide (30%). The flow rate of Ca and P solutions was controlled by using the liquid flow meter. The mixed solution was re-pumped from the outlet into the high gravity set-up and mixed thoroughly with an rpm of 1500 and the process was repeated for two times.

TiO₂ colloidal solution was prepared as follows: 1M of titanium tetra isopropoxide (TTIP) was mixed together with 4 M of acetic acid. The resultant solution was mixed with 10M of double distilled water and the solution was stirred vigorously for 1 h to obtain a clear solution. After an aging period of 24 h, the solution was kept in an oven at 70°C for 12 h to obtain Ti(OH)₄ colloidal solution.

HAp/TiO₂ nanocomposite was prepared from HAp and Ti(OH)₄ colloidal solutions by pumping them through two different solution inlets into a high gravity set-up. The mixed HAp/TiO₂ solution with different TiO₂ proportion of 0,10, 20, 60 and 100 wt% was transferred to the Teflon beaker of the stainless steel autoclaves and placed in an oven at 180°C for 12h and then cooled to room temperature naturally. The final precipitate was washed several times with distilled water and dried at 100°C overnight. The samples were calcinated at 600°C for 1h before further characterization.

3 Characterizations

The prepared samples were structurally characterized by x-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis using a Cu-K α_1 radiation (RIGAKU, D/MAX-2200). The morphology, particle size and size distribution of particles were investigated by a Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FESEM JEOL JSM-6500) at 10 kV after sputtering coating platinum for conduction. To gain further insight into the microstructures, Transmission Electron Microscopic (TEM) investigations were performed using JEOL JEM-2100. Samples for TEM analysis were prepared by air-drying a drop of a sonicated suspension of the dried precipitate in ethanol onto copper grids.

2.3 In vitro cellular assay

The biocompatible property of the prepared HAp nanorods was evaluated in terms of cell

proliferation. Chinese hamster ovary CHO cells (CHO-K1, Korean Collection for Type Cultures), the model animal cell, were used to study the cell compatibility of various HAp/TiO₂ nanocomposite powders. 3M adhesion tape was coated with the nanocomposite powders to study the cell compatibility. The prepared films were washed with PBS for 24 h and were then placed at the bottom of the wells of a multi-well tissue culture plate. After removing the PBS solution from the multiwell tissue culture plate by pipetting, the CHO cells (4×10^4 cm⁻²) were seeded to the film surfaces. Ham's F-12 nutrient mixture (Gibco Laboratories) containing 5% fetal bovine serum, 100 U/mL penicillin and 100 μ g/mL gentamycin was used as the culture medium. The cells were cultured in an incubator at 37 °C under a 5% CO₂ atmosphere. At the end of each incubation period, the supernatant was withdrawn and each well was washed with PBS and treated with trypsin (0.05% trypsin/0.02% ethylenediamine-tetra-acetic acid, Gibco). The morphology of the cultured cells, which were fixed in 2.5% glutaraldehyde solution, was observed using a JEOL JSM-7000F scanning electron microscope (SEM).

2.4 Antimicrobial Activity

The HAp/TiO₂ bio-nano-composites were tested for antimicrobial activity by well-diffusion method against pathogenic organisms such as *Escherichia coli* (*E-coli*) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S-aureus*). The pure cultures of organisms were sub-cultured on Muller-Hinton broth at 35 °C on a rotary shaker at 200 rpm. Wells of 6-mm diameter were made on Muller-Hinton agar (MHA) plates using a sterile well cutter. (MHA plate was prepared as follows: about 3.8 gms of Mueller Hinton agar and 2gms of agar were mixed with 100ml of distilled water in a 250 ml Erlenmeyer flask and were sterilized and 20ml of the media was poured to each of the sterile petridish and allowed for solidification). After solidification of the agar plate, different types of test pathogens were swabbed in each of the agar plate using sterile cotton buds and labeled clearly. A 100- μ l sample of bacterial suspension cultured in nutrient broth (NB) (with a concentration of 10⁵ or 10⁷ CFU/ml of *E. coli* and *S. aureus*) was plated on a nutrient agar plate. The plates were then supplemented with different nanocomposites and incubated at 37°C for 24 h of incubation to observe the zone of inhibition.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 X-ray diffraction analysis

Fig. 1 (a-e) shows the XRD patterns of samples with different compositions of HAp/TiO₂ nanocomposites annealed at 600 °C for 1 h. All the diffraction peaks could be readily indexed with the pure hexagonal phase which is in accordance with the bulk HAp crystals (JCPDS # 09-0432) with lattice parameters

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of HAp/TiO₂ nanocomposites: (a) pure HAp, (b) 10% TiO₂, (c) 20% TiO₂, (d) 60% TiO₂ and (e) pure TiO₂.

of $a = 9.418 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 6.884 \text{ \AA}$. The average crystallite size of all the samples was calculated by Scherrer's formula as 35 nm. In pure TiO₂, the peak positions and their relative intensities are consistent with the standard powder diffraction patterns of anatase-TiO₂ (JCPDS # 21-1272) with a lattice parameter of $a=3.785 \text{ \AA}$; $c=9.513 \text{ \AA}$ (tetragonal). The peak intensity of anatase phase increases with the increase of TiO₂ concentration in the HAp/TiO₂ nanocomposite. At the same time, the intensity of the HAp peak decreases. It is also noted that, the 2θ value of the HAp is shifted slightly towards lower angle region as the wt% of TiO₂ is increased. This is

due to the inclusion of the TiO₂ into the HAp rods which induces the heterogeneous nucleation and shifts the peak towards the TiO₂ position.

3.2 Electron microscopic analysis

The FESEM and TEM micrographs give clear insight to the morphological changes due to the addition of TiO₂ to HAp. Fig. 2(a) shows the microstructure of the HAp with 10 wt% of TiO₂. The addition of TiO₂ influences the formation of longer HAp rods due to the heterogeneous nucleation (see Fig.2e for pristine HAp nanorods). The addition of TiO₂ influences the formation of longer HAp rods due to the heterogeneous nucleation (Fig.1a). Also it is noticed that, the TiO₂ nanoparticles started to deposit on the surface of the HAp nanorods (Fig.1b). It is confirmed that the nanocrystalline TiO₂ is necessary to induce the formation of longer HAp rods which is considered to be a heterogeneous nucleation. Under this

Fig.2. Micrographs of HAp/TiO₂ nanocomposites: FESEM images of (a) 10% TiO₂, (b) 20% TiO₂, (c) 60% TiO₂ and TEM images of (d) 60% TiO₂ (e) pure HAp (d) pure TiO₂.

preparation condition, hydroxyapatite is stable³ and excess of Ti(OH)₄ was easily hydrolyzed as TiO₂,

then nucleated and grown as anatase nanospheres like crystals on HAp surface¹⁵. As the wt% of the TiO₂ is increased to 20% (Fig. 3(b)) there is further increase in the size of the HAp nanorods (aspect ratio ~22) and also the TiO₂ deposition. Fig. 3(c) shows the SEM image of the 60% TiO₂ added composite which clearly shows the deposition of small spheres like TiO₂ crystals with uniform shape and size and with a diameter of 10-15 nm on HAp nanorods. 60% TiO₂ addition further increases the deposition of the TiO₂ on the surface of the HAp. The pristine HAp nanorods are around 120-150 nm in length and 20-25 nm in width as seen in Fig.2 (e). Aspect ratio of the pristine HAp nanorods is about 5. The morphology of the pure nanocrystalline anatase TiO₂ is shown in Fig. 2(f) and it is entirely different from that of the spherical shape shown in the inset which is recorded after adding to HAp. This confirms that TiO₂ is necessary to induce the growth of HAp nanorods with high aspect ratio, which is considered to be a heterogeneous nucleation and it also changes the morphology of the TiO₂. It is much easier than spontaneous homogeneous nucleation¹⁵. The detailed mechanism is discussed elsewhere¹⁴

3.2 In vitro Cellular Assay:

Practically the HAp/TiO₂ composite system has been tried by a few groups¹⁶⁻¹⁸. The composites were reported to have improved mechanical properties¹⁴.

Fig.3. SEM morphologies of the CHO cells grown on (a) pure HAp, (b) 10, (c) 20 and (d) 60 % TiO₂ added HAp/TiO₂ composite.

The biological properties of the HAp/TiO₂ nanocomposites were assessed by measuring the *in*

vitro cellular responses, using osteoblast-like CHO animal cells. Fig. 3 shows the electron micrographs of CHO cells grown on the HAp/TiO₂ nanocomposites, after culturing for 24 h. The cells spread and grew favorably on the composite sample. The growth morphologies on the composite are quite similar to that on pure HAp nanorods (Fig. 3a). Of all the samples, the CHO cells proliferation actively is high on low TiO₂ added samples. For higher TiO₂ concentrated samples the proliferation activity was low.

There are many parameters such as the concentration of HAp and TiO₂¹⁹, preparation methods²⁰, microstructures²¹ that influences the osteoblast cells growth. Ramires *et al* reported that with TiO₂/HAp =1 in the coating weight increases the osteoblast-like cells compared to lower and higher weight (ie., TiO₂/HAp =0.5 and 2)¹⁹. In contrast, in our HAp/TiO₂ nanocomposite powders, the cell growth is decreased with the increasing of TiO₂ concentration. In our case, as the TiO₂ concentration increases the TiO₂ nanoparticles are started depositing on the surface of the HAp nanorods. Hence the surface of the HAp was covered by the TiO₂ particles. This may affect the initial growth and hence decrease the spread of the cell growth. Ramires *et al* further reported that the presence of hydroxyl groups, such as Ti-OH, detected on the coatings surface, could promote the interactions with bone cells by providing the site for calcium and phosphate nucleation¹⁹. But, in our case the reverse process takes. That is Ti(OH)₄ was converted into TiO₂ by hydrolysis in the hydrothermal method. This may reduce the hydroxyl group which provides the site with calcium and phosphate nucleation. Sato *et al* reported that the hydrothermal treatment promotes osteoblast cell adhesion by increasing the level of calcium in HAp²⁰. Our synthesis method was hydrothermal and hence there was an increased growth of cells in the higher HAp concentration due to the increased level of calcium.

3.3 Anti-microbial Activity:

Figs. 4 and 5 show the photographs of the anti microbial activity of HAp/TiO₂ nanocomposite and pristine nanoparticles. The mean of four replicates of the inhabitation zones with diameter of a few millimeters around each well with HAp/TiO₂ composite is used to study the activity. The highest antimicrobial activity was observed against S.

aureus followed by *e-coli* for all samples. The 60 % TiO₂ sample shows very good anti-microbial activity than any other pristine as well as the composite material. Pristine TiO₂ sample shows the next best anti-microbial activity. Other composites have a weak anti-microbial activity, while pristine HAp has the poor anti-microbial activity. Pure and 60% TiO₂ added samples shows good activity against *S. aureus*. It shows less anti bacterial activity against *e-coli*.

Fig. 4: Photographs of the *Staphylococcus aureus* inhabitation zones around (a) pure TiO₂, (b) 60 %, (c) 20 %, (d) 10% TiO₂ and (e) pure HAp.

Fig.5: Photographs of the *Escherichia coli* inhabitation zones around (a) pure TiO₂, (b) 60 % TiO₂ and (c) pure HAp.

The antibiotic activity of the nanocomposites for *S. aureus* was maximum (21 mm) followed by *e-coli* (14 mm). It is clear from the experiment that *S. aureus* is gram-positive and showed the most susceptibility to the nanocomposites in comparison with *e-coli* because it is gram-negative. The strongest indication of the susceptibility of *S. aureus*

to nanocomposites may be a result of their cell wall plasmolysis or the separation of cytoplasm from their cell wall. It was reported that, the Gram-positive bacteria have a relatively thick wall composed of many layers of peptidoglycan polymer, and only one membrane (plasma membrane). The Gram negative bacteria have only a thin layer of peptidoglycan and a more complex cell wall with two cell membranes, an outer membrane, and a plasma membrane. The addition of the outer membrane of the Gram-negative bacteria cells influences the permeability of many molecules. Under certain conditions, the Gram-negative bacteria are more resistant to many chemical agents than Gram-positive cells²².

4. Conclusion:

Bio-nanocomposites of HAp/TiO₂ were successfully prepared by a novel method and their applications in diverse field were tested. The main concentration of this work was on the biocompatibility and antimicrobial activity by varying the TiO₂ concentration. In the lower vol% of TiO₂, the cell growth is excellent and it conforms that it can be used as an implantation material in biomedical field. Further addition of TiO₂ with HAp leads to deposition of TiO₂ as nanospheres on the surface of the HAp nanorods. The excessively TiO₂ added composite was tested for its antimicrobial activity and it was found that the activity was good for gram positive bacteria. The nanocomposites of the present study showed enhanced biocompatibility as well as antimicrobial activity by varying the TiO₂ concentration. So, the nanocomposites of HAp/TiO₂ would be much useful for both in biomedical and environmentally friendly antimicrobial applications due to its better biocompatibility (HAp) and antimicrobial activity (TiO₂).

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